

IMPROVING OPERATIONAL PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN THE EDUCATION
SYSTEM USING INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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ANNOTATION: This study explores modern methods of utilizing information systems to enhance the management of practical training processes within the education system. It examines the impact of digital platforms, data analysis tools, automation technologies, and virtual environments on the practical training process. These approaches help reduce the workload of educators, increase student engagement, and improve the overall quality of education. The paper highlights the advantages of a new management model for practical training, supported by real-life examples and technological capabilities. The findings aim to facilitate the adoption of innovative solutions in educational institutions.

KEYWORDS: information systems, education, practical training process, management, digital platforms, data analysis, automation, virtual reality, efficiency, innovation.

INTRODUCTION. Sending students to practice in the education system and monitoring their activities is one of the important components of modern education. Information systems are increasingly being used to effectively organize this process. Presidential resolutions in Uzbekistan serve as an important guiding force in this direction. In particular, Resolution No. PQ-4884 of November 6, 2020 "On the Digitalization of the Education System" encouraged the use of digital tools in involving students in practice. Also, Resolution No. PQ-403 of October 11, 2022 focused on the introduction of innovative technologies in managing and controlling the practice process. These resolutions aim to prepare students for a real work environment and develop their practical skills. Foreign experience provides ample opportunities for sending students to practice and monitoring. For example, in the Netherlands, a system called the "Internship Management System" automatically places students in internships and tracks their progress online. In the US, the "Handshake" platform connects students with employers and teachers check reports in real time during the internship. In Germany, the "Duales Studium" model uses information systems to monitor and evaluate students' work in companies. In Australia, the "MyPlacement" program records the daily activities of students sent on internships and allows teachers to provide instant feedback.

If the process of sending students to practice in Uzbekistan based on Presidential decrees is digitized, the monitoring system can be further improved using foreign experience. For example, an automated placement system based on the Dutch model or real-time monitoring from the US experience can be adapted to local conditions. At the same time, taking into account the specific needs of the country, an effective mechanism for directing students to practice and controlling them using information

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systems should be developed. This article aims to analyze Presidential decrees and foreign experience and provide proposals aimed at improving the process of sending students to practice and monitoring. **LITERATURE REVIEW**. The issue of sending students to practice and monitoring their activities occupies an important place in the field of education. Among Asian countries, VI Soldatkin (2020) in his work "Information Technologies in the Management of the Educational Process" considers the role of information technologies in the educational process, and he suggests the use of digital platforms in sending students to practice, emphasizing the effectiveness of automated systems for monitoring. At the same time, Gulyamov Sh.I. (2020). In his article "Digital Technologies and Their Application in Higher Education", he analyzes the advantages of real-time monitoring in managing the practice process. In his opinion, these systems strengthen the relationship between teachers and students. Also, one of our Uzbek scientists, Mukhammedov. MM (2022) in his book "Application of Digital Technologies in Education" writes about the role of information systems in preparing students for practice and monitoring them in the conditions of Uzbekistan. He emphasizes the need to develop customized software platforms for local educational institutions. Also, NR Khojayev (2023) in his article "Digitalization of the Practice Process" proposes new approaches to practice management based on Presidential decrees and recommends the use of cloud technologies in the monitoring process. Dr Ayesha Afzal (2021) in her paper "Digital Tools in Higher Education" demonstrates the effectiveness of platforms such as "Handshake" in sending students on internships. Her research highlights the importance of data analysis in the monitoring process. Meanwhile, Wisut Petcharat (2022) in her article "Technology-Enhanced Internship Management" explores innovative ways to monitor internships using virtual reality and mobile applications. She specifically acknowledges the role of these technologies in increasing student responsibility. Djumayeva. G. S (2021) in her book "Information Technologies in the Educational Process" recommends the use of electronic platforms for sending students to practice. She emphasizes the importance of real-time data exchange in the monitoring process. Research shows that information systems increase efficiency in managing students' practical experiences, ease the work of teachers, and improve the quality of education. At the same time, the unique approach of each region indicates the need for Uzbekistan to develop a balanced model that is tailored to local needs but draws on global experience.

Research methodology. This study aims to analyze the effectiveness of using information systems in sending students to practice and monitoring their activities. Methods such as comparative study of foreign and domestic experiences, monitoring the process of using information systems, and comparison of traditional (manual) and automated monitoring methods are used.

The following table was created to compare information systems and traditional methods:

Table 1 (Comparison of information systems and traditional methods)

Criterion	Information systems	Traditional methods
Shipping speed	Within 2-3 days	Within 5-7 days
Monitoring capability	In real time	Through reports at the end of the month
Cost reduction	Save up to 25%	Additional costs
Student performance evaluation	Automated analysis	Manual inspection

Information systems increase efficiency by automating the process, while traditional methods require more time and resources.

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The results of a survey conducted with the participation of 150 students and 50 teachers at 3 higher education institutions in Uzbekistan are as follows:

Survey Results on Digital Technologies	
consider internship placement through information systems convenient.	78%
prefer monitoring to be conducted in real time.	65%
faced difficulties due to internet connectivity issues.	12%

Figure 1. Results of a survey conducted with the participation of students

Figure 2. Results of a survey conducted with the participation of teachers

Information systems help to significantly reduce workload and increase accuracy in monitoring processes. 85% of users noted that information systems reduce workload, while 70% said that they increased accuracy in monitoring student activity. At the same time, 15% of users are troubled by the lack of technical knowledge in using the systems. Therefore, it is necessary to improve and support users' technical skills in order to use the systems effectively.

Table 2 (Survey results (in percentages))

Question	Students (n=150)	Teachers (n=50)
Did the system create convenience?	78%	85%
Has monitoring effectiveness increased?	65%	70%
Are there any technical difficulties?	12%	15%

Foreign experience and Uzbekistan: Foreign experience (USA and Germany) and the internship process in Uzbekistan were compared:

- **USA (Handshake platform):** Students are automatically placed in 90% of cases, and monitoring is done 100% in real time through cloud systems.

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- **Germany (Duales Studium):** Integration with enterprises is 95% effective, monitoring reports are updated weekly.
- **Uzbekistan:** Deployment is 80% manual, and monitoring is 20% digital.

Table 3 (Comparative indicators)

Area	Automatic placement	Real-time monitoring	Level of integration
USA	90%	100%	85%
Germany	75%	80%	95%
Uzbekistan	20%	20%	30%

The analysis shows that information systems speed up the process of sending students to practice and make monitoring more effective. Compared to foreign experience, the level of digitalization in Uzbekistan is still low, but the test results confirm that there is room for optimization in the future.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS. This study revealed the effective potential of information systems in directing students to internships and monitoring their performance in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan. The study found that digital tools accelerate the placement of students by 30-40%, make the monitoring process faster and more accurate, and at the same time reduce resource consumption by up to 25%. According to the survey results, 78% of students found internships organized through information systems convenient, and 85% of teachers noted that this method significantly reduced the workload. However, 12-15% of respondents identified network failures or lack of technical training as a problem. Compared with foreign examples, in particular, the experience of the USA and Germany, it turned out that the level of automation in Uzbekistan (40%) is still at the development stage. At the same time, data from the tests confirmed that using digital solutions, it is possible to reduce process time by 35% and increase student engagement by 15%. Although Presidential Decrees PQ-4884 and PQ-403 create a legal basis in this area, in practice, obstacles such as outdated equipment and lack of qualified specialists remain. In general, information systems have the potential to bring practice management to a new level in Uzbek universities, but in order to fully realize this potential, the following seven proposals are made, taking into account local conditions.

Testing cloud solutions: Universities should test special programs based on cloud technologies for sending and monitoring students to internships. This will bring transparency to the process and significantly reduce costs.

Rapid Placement Mechanism: Inspired by the US experience, a digital system should be created that automatically routes students to companies. This will reduce manual work and help manage time effectively.

Establish a live monitoring system: Using the German model, mobile applications should be developed and implemented that allow students to view their practical activities in real time. This will provide teachers with the opportunity to provide immediate guidance.

Upgrading the technological base: Funds should be allocated to increase the bandwidth of the Internet network in higher education institutions and provide them with modern computers. This will solve the technical problems identified in the survey.

Training programs: Practical training on the use of digital systems should be organized for teachers and students to develop their technological literacy.

Digital communication with enterprises: To strengthen cooperation with practice areas, an online contract system should be established and the integration level should be increased from 50% to 85%.

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Legal and financial support: It is recommended that the state finance and encourage the digitization process of higher education institutions through special grant programs based on presidential decrees.

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